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STUDY OF QUANTITATIVE APPROACH ON WAGE DIFFERENTIATION OF WORKER IN PAPUA PROVINCE

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Abstract. Inequitable distribution of income is an essential issue in the development plan because it has a direct link to welfare. Papua is one of the provinces that are dealing with this issue. It is known from both indicators which the work participation rate and the poverty rate were high. Therefore, this study will describe the factors that influence the wage differentials of workers in Papua so that the government has a more accurate picture of policy steps. This study uses the classification and regression tree (CART) analysis of the 2019 National Labor Force Survey (SAKERNAS). The results of the study show that from five predictor variables used, four of them can explain the phenomenon of wage differentiation in Papua. The four variables are the use of IT in employment, business sector, gender, and education level. In the meantime, rural-urban classification variables do not have a substantial role in influencing workers' wage differentiation. Based on the results of the study, the government should make a long-term investment in improving the quality of human resources, and making regulations that are pro to gender equality. They also should focus on efforts to penetrate technology in the business, and create the relevant programs to boost the added value in the sector of agriculture.

Keywords: Welfare, Workforce, Income Distribution, Classification and Regression Tree (CART).

INTRODUCTION

In the development plan, wage has become an essential issue for the community (Gottvald et al., 2013). It may happen because the wages have a direct bearing on the welfare of a worker (Asmara, 2017). The number of wages received will affect the purchasing power of the worker.

Papua, as one of the provinces in Indonesia in August 2019, was recorded to have a workforce participation rate by 76.92 per cent and an open unemployment rate by 3.65 per cent (BPS-Statistics Papua, 2019). This figure is quite good compared to other provinces. Even so, it turns out with the poverty rate as the highest in Indonesia, which is 26.55 per cent (BPS-Statistics Indonesia, 2020). The contradiction in the achievement of these two indicators should suspect that the existence of jobs in Papua cannot provide a decent income for some workers. At least, there is a differentiation of wages among workers, which some workers earned a decent income, while other workers earn a low income.

As the initial hypothesis, many factors affected the number of wages received by workers. Referring to the results of a study conducted by Lukmanasari & Soemardi (2016) on construction workers in Java showed that the level of wages influenced by company profile, project profile, and worker profile. Furthermore, Miswar (2018) found that the wage differentials of workers in Aceh caused by education, type of work, number of hours worked, and work experience. Meanwhile, Gibbs (2017) shows that the existence of technology has an impact on labour market polarization. The workforce who have high skills will get a high wage increase, while workers with low skills remain stagnant with the previous wage.

Apart from the previous three studies, the business sector classification, urban-rural classification, and gender bias also thought to have influenced wage differentiation. Referring to the results of the study Arrofi (2020) shows that workers in the agricultural sector have lower wages than workers in the non-agricultural sector. Another research from Pertiwi's (2015) shows that urban workers tend to get higher wages than the rural worker. As for the relationship between gender and wages received, several studies conducted show that as generally, the women receive lower wages than men (Istiqomah & Budiani, 2019; Mardiana, 2015; Wirartha, 2000).

All of these previous studies are relevant in explaining the current issue of wage differentiation. However, it conducted with scope outside of Papua. Therefore, it is necessary to re-test the effectiveness of the influence of these variables on the phenomenon in Papua. In this research, many aspects possible to make a different conclusion with previous studies. It depends on the socio-economic conditions of the community as well as other things that are unique.

Quantitative study on wage differentiation in Papua need to carry out. The urgency of conducting this research is to facilitate provincial and regency/city governments to obtain an overview of the intervening way in pro-welfare policies. Simple and effective analysis-modelling are needed so that the policies would take precisely.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Wages are compensation paid for worker productivity (Otobo, 1987). In the production process, the economic actors require various factors of production, one of which is labour. So, based on the Cobb-Douglas production function, the existence of labour has a stake in producing output (Hajkova & Hurnik, 2007). As a consequence of workforce productivity, the economic actor will pay a wage to the worker.

Along with the development of civilization and technology, the demand for labour expertise is increasingly diverse (Hyclak et al., 2012). Based on Human capital theory, the diversity of expertise has an impact on the different income distribution between the various job (Neal & Rosen, 2000). Nevertheless, theoretically that the unequal distribution of income can minimize through strengthening skills (Tinbergen, 1973) and supporting government political policies (Greenlaw & Shapiro, 2016; Stewart, 2000).

METHODOLOGY

The Scope of Research and Variable

The data used in this study from the second Semester 2019 of National Labor Survey (SAKERNAS) in 29 regencies/cities in Papua Province from BPS-Statistics Indonesia. The number of samples included in the survey was 39,763 households spread throughout the Papua Province. The sample selection in this survey is a proportional sample that is Proportional to Size (PPS), and Systematic Sampling has chosen at the regional level, namely national and district/city.

The response variable used is the number of wages in rupiah. While the predictor variables used consisted of preference IT used in the workplace (digitalisasi), level of education (pendidikan), gender (jk), urban-rural classification (klasifikasi), and the economic sector (tiga_sektor). In detail, each of the variables as the following table.

Table 1. Details of the Variables Used

Variable	Scale	Category
Wage	Ratio	-
IT Usage	Nominal	1. Yes 2. No
Education	Ordinal	1. No more than senior high school 2. College/University
Sex	Nominal	1. Male

Variable	Scale	Category
		2. Female
Rural-Urban Classification	Nominal	1. Rural 2. Urban
Economic Sector	Nominal	1. Agriculture 2. Manufacture 3. Service

Analysis Method

The analytical method used in this study is the Classification and Regression Tree (CART). This method used to find out the characteristics distinguish the level of wage workers in Papua. The way to get the factors that influence the difference in wage rates, an approach using tree regression analysis is performed.

An examination of the influence of independent variables on the dependent often uses the classical regression analysis method. However, the validity of classical regression is very much dependent on many conditions like assumptions that need to meet. The assumptions are intervals minimum scale must meet, the assumptions of linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, non-multicollinearity, and non-autocorrelation. With a regression tree, we can do an exploration of the relationship between the two types of variables with different types of data (nominal, ordinal, interval, and ratio) without regard to all forms of assumptions (Komalasari, 2007).

The difference with the classical regression, the regression tree explains the effect of explanatory variables and the estimation of their responses to the groups of observations determined based on explanatory variables. That way, the interpretation becomes easier. The identification effect of explanatory variables of this method is carried out in each subgroup of data, not in the aggregate data as well as in classical regression. Furthermore, the regression tree by itself can overcome the problem of data exclusion. Another case with the classic regression that can not overcome the problem of data exclusion. Whereas data outliers can cause changes in data distribution, event damage estimation results. If not eliminated, the results of the classical regression estimation will be biased and not by the actual population (Komalasari, 2007).

Meanwhile, the software used in the data processing combined between SPSS and R. R statistical software as a main tool has provided a program to analyze data using the regression tree technique, the package tree which can find in the tool menu and choose the install packages. There are several steps to conducting an R analysis in this study:

Creating Regression Tree

In the running, the regression tree method in R uses the tree function. To print the results, we need the print command, as well as the summary command to

display the data description. Next, plot and text commands are needed to display the regression diagram along with the information. Following is the display of the R running code in this study:

```
> mydata<-tree::tree(upah~jk+klasifikasi+pendidikan
+tiga_sektor+digitalisasi, data_sak19, data_sak19$w
eight)
```

```
> summary(mydata)
```

Regression tree:

```
tree::tree(formula = upah ~ jk + klasifikasi +
pendidikan + tiga_sektor + digitalisasi, data =
data_sak19, weights = data_sak19$weight)
```

Variables actually used in tree construction:

```
[1] "digitalisasi" "tiga_sektor"
```

```
[3] "jk" "pendidikan"
```

Number of terminal nodes: 5

Residual mean deviance: 6.495e+12 = 4.537e+18 / 698500

Distribution of residuals:

```
Min. 1st Qu. Median Mean 3rd Qu.
-4829000 -1466000 -665100 -127800 634900
Max.
44600000
```

```
> print(mydata)
```

node), split, n, deviance, yval

* denotes terminal node

```
1) root 698520 5.289e+18 3338000
2) digitalisasi: tidak 435828 2.068e+18 2709000
4) tiga_sektor: tani 186449 5.901e+17 1966000 *
5) tiga_sektor: manuf,jasa 249379 1.297e+18
3265000 *
3) digitalisasi: pakai 262692 2.762e+18 4383000
6) jk: L 185280 2.314e+18 4677000
12) pendidikan: SD,SMP,SMA_SMK 116116
1.095e+18 4245000 *
13) pendidikan: PT 69164 1.161e+18 5402000 *
7) jk: P 77412 3.938e+17 3677000 *
```

```
> plot(mydata); text(mydata)
```

Fig. 1. Regression Tree Chart from R Code Running of the Data Research

The summary results and Figure 1 show that not all variables in the model can use to form a regression tree. Then, the printout command produces the results of the tree function in the form of many observations,

the number of squares (deviations), and the average value on each cover. The plot command will display the chart, and the text command will display the information in the chart.

Pruning Tree

The more vertices in a regression tree will complicate the tree structure. To overcome these problems pruning trees is needed. In R, tree trimming can do with the prune tree function. The function can show the plot of reducing deviance to the increasing number of vertices (Breiman et al., 2017). Here are the results of running tree pruning in R:

```
> plot(tree::prune.tree (mydata))
```

Fig. 2. Pruning Tree Plot

The plot above shows the development of pruning tree nodes to their deviations. The more tree branches, the less deviance the model produced. Then, the smallest deviance obtained when node formation is at node 5. Even the arrangement of the nodes also stops at the 5th

node. It shows that further tree node formation will no longer reduce deviance.

Based on these facts, it can conclude that tree pruning is not necessary anymore. It is because the number of regression tree nodes at the beginning of formation and inspection of tree pruning plots show that the formation of the 5th node is an ideal function, with the least deviance.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The resulting plot results in Figure 3 show that not all independent variables enter the compilation of the tree regression model. From five explanatory variables, one variable is unused, namely the classification of rural-urban (klasifikasi). That means that regardless of the type of area where Papuan labours work, both urban and rural, it will not affect the value of wages earned. This fact is natural in Papua Province because the percentage of urban areas is tiny at only 2.9 per cent. When compared, it is in sharp contrast with rural areas which reach 97.1 per cent (BPS-Statistics Papua, 2018).

Back in Figure 3, the regression tree makes the first node in the IT-Usage variable (digitalisasi). This fact shows that the most influential variable in determining the wage value of workers in Papua is the use of computer technology. Although rural mostly cover almost all of the Papua area, this does not mean that the use of computer technology is not essential. In line with Borghans & ter Weel (2001), the higher the skill of using an employee's computer, the higher the wage value he receives.

Similarly, the study of Brown & Campbell (2002) shows that the use of technology and computerization at work

Fig. 3. The Result of Tree Classification

Note: a) Rp 2,709,183 b) Rp 4,382,516 c) Rp 4,677,246 d) Rp 3,677,100
e) Rp 1,965,672 f) Rp 3,265,071 g) Rp 4,245,000 h) Rp 5,402,000

has changed the structure of labour market demand. The demand for companies for workers with digital skills is increasing. Demand also provides compensation in the form of an increase in the number of wages offered by the company.

The difference in wages is very striking depending on the IT skills of workers. Based on Figure 3, Groups of workers who use computers have an average wage of 4,832,516 rupiahs. Very far, when compared labours who do not use computer technology, which only has an average wage of 2,709,183 rupiahs. The existence of income inequality shows that even though Papua is the least developed province in Indonesia, it does not mean the use of computerized technology is not needed there. It is precisely this ability that has a high bargaining value in determining the value of wage workers in Papua.

Now the focus is on grouping workers who do not utilize computer technology. Differences in wage structures within this group also separated into two groups. First is the group of workers who work in the agricultural sector; second is the manufacturing and service sectors.

The worker cluster in the agricultural sector has an average value of wages is lower than the manufacturing and service sector groups. The agricultural sector workers group has an average wage of around 1,965,672 rupiahs, while workers in the manufacturing and service sectors are much higher at 3,265,071 rupiahs.

This finding also supported by the results of Gollin et al., (2014) about the income gap between the agricultural sector and other sectors in developing countries. The difference in gaps thought to be due to the low value-added generated (Arham, 2020) and the low level of productivity (Emran & Shilpi, 2016) in the agricultural sector. Therefore, the existence of training to increase productivity becomes very important for the agricultural sector (Adeyemo & Okoruwa, 2018).

Additional information, agricultural workforces have the lowest average wage structure in the regression tree model. It shows that agricultural labours are the group who have the lowest income compared to all employment sectors in Papua Province.

BPS-Statistics Papua (2019) noted that the agricultural sector controls 67.73 per cent of the labour market in Papua. The low wage structure of farmers in Papua makes the majority of the population in Papua unequal. The agricultural sector, which has a base in rural areas, produce pockets of poverty. It is apparent, Papua Province became the poorest province in Indonesia.

Referring again to the IT skills variable, it is true that workers who master computer skills have an average income value higher than non-IT workers. However, that does not mean there is no imbalance in it. Inequality does not occur in differences in educational strata but gender. There is an income gap between men and women who master computer skills. The average income of men who

have IT skills ranges from 4,677,246 rupiahs, while women are far below that is only around 3,677,100 rupiahs. Income difference reaches one million rupiahs.

The regression tree does not see any difference in income inequality between men and women for jobs that do not involve IT skills, while those that involve IT skill show wage level contrasts. It provides a visualization that gender bias only occurs in more present-time jobs. While in traditional work, gender bias does not occur. The occurrence of gender discrimination is allegedly due to stereotypes that are still inherent in the community related to the competency gap between the two types of gender (Blau & Kahn, 2017).

For men who work with IT, high education affects the number of wages received compared to male workers with lower education. Education is one of the differentiators of the number of wages received because it is closely related to the competencies possessed by employees (Kunartinah & Sukoco, 2010). In the tree regression model clearly shows the average value of wages of male workers with education strata equivalent to elementary, junior high, and high school/vocational school (4,245,000 rupiahs) less than the equivalent level of higher education (5,402,000 rupiahs).

Not commensurate with male workers, female workers who have computer skills with different levels of education will not change their wage structure. It shows that the placement of women in jobs that involve computers seems haphazard in Papua. Chances are, there is a kind of stereotype that considers female computer skills with any educational background more minor than men. That way, the placement of women in work is always below the men.

CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation in the previous chapter, we know that the differentiation of wages in Papua occurred. The results of this study indicate that the lowest average wages are obtained by workers in the agricultural sector who do not use technology in their work activities. Meanwhile, the highest wages are received by educated people who worked in jobs position that uses the IT-supporting. Generally, there are five classes of wage differentiation formed and influenced by four predictor variables, viz: using IT, business sector, gender, and education. As for the geographical variable, which is represented by the urban-rural classification does not show the effect on wage differentiation.

Follow up the findings of this study; four suggestions should be executed by the government, viz: (1) the government should invest in human resources through skills training and education relevant to expertise in the industrial activity, (2) the government needs to formulate the regulations and implement it effectively for the business actor regarding performance-based compensation and not biased towards gender, (3) the

government must help the businesses actor to engage in technological literacy, and (4) the government needs to make various relevant programs such as mentoring and subsidizing the raw materials to increase competitiveness and economic value-added, especially in the agricultural sector.

For the next study, we advised the researchers who are interested in wage and employment issues to explore more the readiness of the business unit to adapt to technological exchange. It is quite urgent, considering that currently, IT classification is the main differentiating factor for wages received by workers. Also, to obtain a more comprehensive analysis, panel data with more extended data series should be used.

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